

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL HAIR OIL

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ABSTRACT

Herbal formulations always have activity and comparatively lesser or no side effects with synthetic. The growth activity in a concentration range for 1-10% separately. Based on these results mixture of crude drugs fruits of *Embelica officinalis*, flowers of *Hibiscus rosasinensis*, leaves of *ocimum sanctum*, *azadirecta indica* and seeds of *Trigonella foenumgraecum* were prepared in the form of herbal hair oil by boiling cloth method and were tested for hair growth activity, refractive index, acid value, saponification value. It holds the promise of potent herbal alternative for synthetic hair oils. Excellent results of hair growth were seen in formulation prepared by boiling method of oils preparation technique. The Herbal cosmetics are nowadays widely used because of fewer side effects with better safety and security. The present work was aimed to formulate polyherbal hair oil for general purpose using various Herbs. Herbal hair oil was prepared from the hair growth. The Formulation were also subjected to chemical test determination. To determine the presence of active constituent in the drug. Excellent result of hair growth were seen in formulation.

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INTRODUCTION

Hair is one of the vital parts of our body and it influences the overall appearance of person. Hair is a protein filament that grows from follicles found in the dermis. Hair is one of the most important of our body that improves the overall appearance of person. The hair fall, dandruffs, split ends, grey hair are the major problem associated with hair. Hair loss is distressing condition for an increasing number of men and women. Hair loss is or alopecia, is a common patient problems/complaint. And a source of significant psychological and physical distress. To overcome this problems, we use lots of hair care products use.

In traditional Indian system of medicine many plants and herbal formulations are reported for hair growth promotion as well as improvement of quality of hair. Herbal care products are defined as those formulation which are used for cleansing, modifying the texture of hair, changing of colour, giving life to stressed hair and providing nourishment of the hair. Hair oils are the hair care formulations applied for treatment of hair disorders such as baldness, aggression of hair discoloring of hair, hair falling, dryness of hair. Herbal hair oils are formulated with herbal extracts in oil base.

Herbal hair oil is more preferred and is used in many ailments of hair. They promote hair growth, improve elegance of hair and prevent hair fall. Hair oil not only promotes hair growth they also provide necessary moisture to the scalp rendering in beautiful hair. The present work was aimed to prepare and evaluate a polyherbal hair oil containing herbs like curry leaves, amla, hibiscus, neem, tulsi, fenugreek in coconut oil. All these herbs have well known traditional potential in the treatment of hair care.

The hair fall, Dandruffs, split ends, grey hair are the major problem associated with hair. To overcome these problems, we use lots of cosmetics. Among these, hair loss (alopecia) is a universal problem having affected both sexes of all races to different extents for as long as mankind has existed. The hair care industry has become aware of this and delivering active products directed towards meeting this consumer demand. In traditional Indian system of medicine many plants and herbal formulations are reported for hair growth promotion as well as improvement of quality of hair.

In our study, we have formulated herbal hair oils from *Embelica officinalis*, flowers of *Hibiscus rosasinensis*, leaves of *Bacopamonnieri* and seeds of *Trigonella foenumgraecum*, and Coconut oil used for the best medicine of hair growth.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Collection And Authentication Of Plant Materials

The Polyherbal hair oil was prepared by collecting and using various plant materials these are, hibiscus rosasinensis leaf, curry leaf, amla, Fenugreek seeds, tulsi leaves, neem leaves, coconut oil, are collected from local market near Nanded. aloe Vera leaf were collected from Botanical Garden Of D K PATIL INSTITUTE OF PHARMACY, LOHA. Collected plants were identified by our guide Ms. P. D. Pawale mam. The collected leaves were dried in the shade and then powder to coarse consistency and stored in an air tight container at room temperature.

PLANT PROFILE

HIBISCUS FLOWER

Kingdom - Plantae -plants

Family – malvaceae

Genus – hibiscus L

Biological name – *hibiscus rosa sinensis*

Chemical Constituents : β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, flavonoids, riboflavin

Uses –

- Hibiscus flowers help to stop hair loss,
- make your hair look healthy and lustrous.
- prevent premature graying.
- thicken hair and add volume, treat dandruff,
- condition against frizz, dryness, and breakage, prevent split ends.

FENUGREEK SEEDS

Kingdom - Plantae -plants

Family – Fabaceae

Genus – Trigonella

Biological name – *Trigonella foenum-graecum* Chemical Constituents : Trigonelline, Diosgenin, Galactomannan , Gitogenin

Uses –

- Reduce the risk of diabetes.
- Improve milk production and flow.

TULSI

Kingdom - Plantae -plants

Family – Lamiaceae

Genus – Ocimum L

Biological name – *Ocimum sanctum*

Chemical Constituents : Eugenia 70%, Alkaloids, Carvacrol 3%, Glycosides, Gitogenin

Uses –

- Tulsi can cure fever
- Tulsi is used to treat insect bites
- Tulsi is also used to treat respiratory problems

NEEM

Kingdom - Plantae -plants

Family – Meliaceae

Genus –

Biological name – *Azadirachta indica*

Chemical constituents - β sitosterol, triterpens, tannins, alkaloids.

Uses –

- Neem is an effective herb to treat hair loss.
- Due to its antibacterial, antifungal and anti-inflammatory properties, neem is an excellent way to curb dandruff.
- It helps the hair follicles to become stronger and also encourages hair growth.

AMLA

Kingdom - Plantae -plants

Family – Phyllanthaceae

Genus – Trigonella

Biological name – *Emblica officinalis*

Chemical Constituents : vitamin c, Alkaloids, amino acid , pectin

Uses –

- It helps in conditioning scalp
- promote healthy hair growth,
- minimize grays, boost volume,
- reduce dandruff.
- hair conditioner, treats scalp ailments.

ALOE VERA

Kingdom - Plantae -plants

Family – Liliaceae

Genus –Aloe L

Biological name – *Aloe barbadensis* , *aloe officinalis*

Chemical Constituents : Aloins, Barbaloins, Iso barbaloins.

Uses –

- Relieves the burned skin caused by skin.
- Smooth and glowing skin can be achieved with the help of Aloe.
- It is an outstanding skin moisturizer.

COCONUT OIL

Kingdom - Plantae -plants

Family – Arecaceae

Genus –Cocos.L

Biological name – *Cocos nucifera*

Chemical Constituents : Lauric Acid 47%, vitamins , minerals.

Uses –

- Raw material for hair oil and hair tonic, moisturizer
- Moisturises hair and scalp,
- reduces and prevents symptoms of scalp psoriasis

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

FORMULATION OF POLYHERBAL HAIR OIL

Table No 01: Formulation Of Polyherbal Hair Oil.

Sr.No.	Ingredients	Quantity	Uses
1.	Hibiscus Flower	7.5	Prevent dandruff
2.	Fenugreek seeds	5	Hair growth
3.	Tulsi leaves	2.5	Strengthen the roots
4.	Neem leaves	2.5	Antimicrobial
5.	Amla	2.5	Hair growth
6.	Triphala	0.75	Prevent premature graying
7.	Coconut oil	Upto 50ml	Vehicle

PROCEDURE

All herbs of crude drugs are collected and dried under shade. Drying under shade will retain active constituents. Hence, shade drying is preferred over artificial drying.

The dried crude drugs were made into coarse powder using mixer. Later on, all these coarsely powdered drugs are passed through Sieve with mesh number 80. this, obtained powders are blended together to get uniform mixture.

Now coconut oil and aloe Vera pulp is added. These all dried powders of mixed well. Now contents were boiled 15min and were filtrated through muslin cloth.

To filtrate, coconut oil was added to make up volume. Finally, prepared polyherbal hair oil. And these are it was placed in ambered colored bottle.

EVALUATION OF HERBAL OIL

The formulated herbal oil was evaluated for parameters like pH, acid value, saponification value, refractive index, viscosity and organoleptic parameters

pH

The pH of herbal hair oil was to be determined by using pH meter.

Organoleptic Property

In these test prepared formulation was proposed to be evaluated for sensory tests like aroma, colour, odour, etc.

Sensitivity Test

The prepared herbal hair oil was applied on 1 cm skin of hand and exposed to sunlight for 4-5 min.

Skin Irritation Test

Prepared Polyherbal Hair Oil was applied on hand and exposed to sunlight for 5mins to check for any irritation over skin.

Storage Stability

The storage stability was carried out for the prepare polyherbal hair oil at a temperature of 37 °C for 5 days.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The formulation and evaluation of polyherbal hair oil using Neem leaves, curry leaves, tulsi leaves, hibiscus flowers, fenugreek seeds, was prepared. The various parameters like color, odour, irritation test, sensitivity test, viscosity, pH of herbal hair oil was evaluated.

The formulated hair oil was evaluated for the physiochemical properties such as color, odour pH from stability the result are as the following:

Table no 2 : Organoleptic characteristics of Polyherbal Hair Oil.

FORMULATION	EVALUATION	OBSERVED
Polyherbal Hair Oil	Colour	Greenish brown
	Odour	Characteristic
	Ph	6.8
	Sensitivity Test	Not sensitive
	Irritation Test	No irritation
	Storage Stability	37 ^{0c}

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study we can conclude that the formulated herbal hair oil can maintain normal function of sebaceous glands and promotes natural hair growth. It can also give antimicrobial, hair growth, hair thickness properties. It can help prevent hair thinning, treat scalp infection. It can help to maintain moisture in scalp and improves blood circulation, reduces itchiness and dryness.

Recommend Future Research

The objective behind development of poly herbal hair oil was to provide an safe efficacious secure alternative for the synthetic and substandard marketed products. The ingredients we proposed in the formulation of the product have been proved helpful in treating dermal problems like. Pigmentation (fading), dandruff, falling of hairs (shedding), hair loss (alopecia), dry hair, dry scalp.

Authors Contributions

PBT: wrote manuscript draft

PBT: manuscript editing, supervision of PDP;

APT,SMS,AGT: literature collection

PDP: supervised whole project and wrote and guided.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATION

OcimumL : Ocimumlactum

C. nucifera : Cocos nucifera

Sr. : Serial

No. : Number

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